

AE4EU

Agroecology for Europe (AE4EU)

Towards the development of agroecology in Europe

Deliverable report D5.1 – Analysis of Policy Implementation at EU Level for Different European Countries and CAP Strategies

Authors of the report	Mosquera-Losada MR, Franco-Grandas T, Ferreiro-Domínguez N, Alvarez-Lopez V, Rodriguez-Rigueiro JJ, Wezel A, Grard B, Schmutz U, Wigboldus S, Donhan J, Migliorini M, Canalil S, Bingol O, Santiago-Freijanes JJ
Contributors to the report	
Grant Agreement Number	101000478
Project acronym and title	AE4EU - Agroecology for Europe
Project website	www.ae4eu.eu
Funding Scheme	Coordination and support action (CSA)
Call identifier	H2020-FNR-2020-1
Topic	FNR-01-2020 Strengthening the European agro-ecological research and innovation ecosystem
Start date of project	January 1st, 2021
Duration	36 months
Project coordinator & organisation	Dr. Alexander Wezel - ISARA, Lyon, France
Lead Partner for deliverable	ISARA
Work package	WP5
Due date of deliverable	31/06/2022
Actual submission date	31/07/2022
Resubmission date	
Dissemination level	Public

Table of Content

<i>Table of Content</i>	2
<i>Table of Illustrations</i>	3
<i>Introduction</i>	5
<i>Agroecology policy definition</i>	5
<i>Agroecology international policies</i>	17
<i>Agroecology European policies</i>	19
<i>Agroecology and the CAP specific objectives, impact indicators, result indicators and output indicators</i> .20	
<i>Economic objectives</i>	20
<i>Social objectives</i>	26
<i>Transversal objectives</i>	28
<i>CAP conditionality, Pillar I, Pillar II and agroecology</i>	28
<i>Conclusions</i>	40
<i>Policy recommendations</i>	41
<i>References</i>	42
ANNEX I	45
ANNEX II	51

Table of Illustrations

Tables

Table 1 Researcher definitions of agroecology (Wezel et al. 2009).....	6
Table 2 International institutions' and organisations' definitions of agroecology	7
Table 3 Definitions of Agroecology used by governments in different countries.....	8
Table 4 Economic Intervention, CAP outputs indicators, FAO elements, CAP objectives and EU strategies dominant relationships.....	23
Table 5 Environmental Intervention, CAP outputs indicators, FAO elements, CAP objectives and EU strategies dominant relationships	26
Table 6 Social Intervention, CAP outputs indicators, FAO elements, CAP objectives and EU strategies dominant relationships.....	28

Table of Illustrations

Figures

Figure 1 Most frequent two-words in the agroecology (top), organic farming (middle) and agroecology+organic (bottom) farming papers	10
Figure 2 Over 0.1% one-wording search distribution of agroecology (top) and organic farming (bottom) within the global (internet + web of science databases).....	11
Figure 3 Share Nitrogen output in the EU countries as average 2005-200s (Eurostat 2011).....	12
Figure 4 Most frequent production 2-keywords in the agroecology (top), organic farming (centre) and agroecology+organic farming wording groups (bottom) for the global (web of science + internet) and research (web of science) searches.....	14
Figure 5 Most frequent environment 2-keywords in the agroecology (top), organic farming (centre) and agroecology+organic farming wording groups (bottom) for the global (web of science + internet) and research (web of science) searches.....	15
Figure 6 Most frequent social 2-keywords in the agroecology (top), organic farming (centre) and agroecology+organic farming wording groups (bottom) for the global (web of science + internet) and research (web of science) searches	16
Figure 7 Post-2020 CAP aims (black), FAO agroecology elements (green) and EU linked strategies (red)	18
Figure 8 Agroecology transition levels (SCAR-AGROECOLOGY, 2022, based on HLPE 2019 and Gliessman 2007)	19
Figure 9 European mountain areas (EEA 2010).....	21
Figure 10 Results of the main plant production practices found in the agroecology and organic farming papers search	31
Figure 11 Results of the main animal production practices found in the agroecology and organic farming papers search	32
Figure 12 Results of the main farm management practices found in the agroecology and organic farming papers search	32
Figure 13 Percentage of the RDP areas covered with annual crops	33
Figure 14 Annual crops evolution changes from cereal crop lands.....	34
Figure 15 Annual crops evolution changes from wheat crop lands.	35
Figure 16 Number of measures promoting rotation with legumes in the RDP of 2014-2020	36
Figure 17 Number of measures promoting winter catch crops in the RDP of 2014-2020.....	37
Figure 18 Annual crops areas percentage covered with two or more crops per RDP area.	38
Figure 19 Number of measures promoting mixed culture and polyculture in the 2014-2020 RDPs..	38
Figure 20 Number of measures promoting agroforestry in the RDP of 2014-2020.	39
Figure 21 RDP programmes activating organic farming measures in the RDP of 2014-2020.	39

Introduction

Transition to Agroecology is being recently considered by the EU as a form to increase sustainability of the European farming systems. It has been recently created the SCAR-Agroecology group that has been working on the definition, relevance and development of a European partnership in agroecology living labs and research infrastructures.

The promotion of agroecology at ground level can be carried out through the development of adequate European policies such as the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). The CAP is the main driver of the agriculture in Europe as it funds farming activities but also rural development. The CAP is based on clear definitions and concrete activities mainly carried out at field but also at food system level, that are not yet established in the concept for agroecology implementation in Europe.

Agroecology is based on the integration of temporary and permanent biodiversity at different spatial levels (plot, farm, landscape) which is not currently and extensively monitored when the payments are carried out. Moreover, the integration of this biodiversity at different spatial levels modifies the agri-food system associated to this specific land management, that must be more diversified and supports better the local market as more products are delivered from the same area. This is especially relevant for the establishment of living labs to jointly analyse the diversified use of the land and their associated and diversified market.

The deliverable 5.1 aims at analysing the agroecology policy implementation at EU level and different European countries and CAP strategies. It has been structured in sections by analysing the agroecology policy definition based on a literature review that considers policy, but also end-users needs and research advances to fully understand the agroecology perception from different perspectives to deliver more targeted policies. The second section evaluates the role of agroecology within the European policies from a global perspective linked to strategies and the post-2020 CAP. The third section analyses how agroecology was fostered in the past considering the rules of the post-2020 CAP. Whenever relevant, the linkages with organic farming as a well established concept was also evaluated.

Due to the delay in delivery the CAP strategies, which will be approved in July 2022, it was not possible to provide a concrete and valid analysis of the CAP strategies at country level. It will be the basis of the next policy report and it is going to be delivered at the end of the project as the basis of EU agroecology strategy that will be adapted at country level.

Agroecology policy definition

Agroecology public bodies definition

According to the FAO (2021) the term «agroecology» has been defined in many ways, in many places, and by many institutions. Since the 1920s, scientists and researchers have used the term agroecology to refer to the application of ecological principles to agriculture. However, it was not until the early-1980s that the discipline of "agroecology" was named by ecologists, agronomists and ethnobotanists. The FAO has gathered the agroecology definitions provided by different countries (Tables, 1, 2 and 3), while an excellent review of agroecology definitions was provided by Wezel et al. (2009).

Table 1. Researcher definitions of agroecology (Wezel et al. 2009)

Altieri, 1995	The science of agroecology is defined as the application of ecological concepts and principles to the design and management of sustainable agroecosystems.
Altieri 1999	Agroecology is a discipline delivering the main basic ecologic to study, design, evaluate and manage agroecosystems to be productive and preserve the natural resources, while being culturally sensible, socially fair and economically viable. Agroecology can be described as a mean that integrate ideas and methods from several sub-fields instead of a specific discipline. Agroecology could be a normative challenge to the way how several disciplines focus on the agricultural challenges. It has the roots on the agricultural science, environmental movement, ecology, indigenous agroecosystems analysis and the rural development studies. Each of these research areas have very different aims and methodologies. However, all them have been influenced by relevant and legitimate agroecology thinking.
Francis et al. 2003	Agroecology is the integrative study of the ecology of the entire food system, encompassing ecological, economic and social dimensions.

Table 1 shows how diverse agroecology can be, starting by the agricultural management and systems (Altieri, 1995), understanding the social movement (Altieri, 1999) and finally including the whole food system (Francis et al. 2003). Moreover, it also demonstrates that different definitions are using and sharing common elements, adjusted to the local circumstances. These common elements are captured by FAO in its framework on agroecology. FAO’s framework of 10 elements of agroecology is derived from the common principles articulated for agroecology, including a combination of bio-physical and socio-economic elements that are grounded in the three pillars of sustainable development – the social, the economic and the environmental. Different elements may have different configurations, with a strong blend of social, economic and environmental aspects.

The research agroecology definition can be structured by the original concept usually framed by agronomy, forestry, biology and ecologist research and by the understanding that agriculture includes a set of ecosystems handled by human beings in a more simple or holistic way (Table 1). This provides a set of international (Table 2) and national definitions (Table 3). The initial research definitions (Table 1) are linked to the ecological principles of sustainable farm designing and managing which, therefore, includes economic, environment and social aspects not only considering the farms but also the entire food system.

Table 2 International institutions' and organisations' definitions of agroecology

OECD, 2003	Agro-ecology is the study of the relation of agricultural crops and environment.
ASA, CSSA, SSSA, 2004	Agroecology is a scientific discipline that seeks to provide an objective, ecologically based assessment of the structure, function, multidimensionality, and special scale of food systems. It is a complex science, one that links the ecological, economic, social, ethical, and legal aspects of food production. All spatial scales are considered, from farm field to global, and systems approaches are emphasized.
Altieri and Nicolls 2005	The Science of Agroecology is defined as the application of ecological concepts and principles to the design and management of sustainable agroecosystems.
Nyeléni - International Forum Agroecology 2015	Agroecology is a way of life and the language of Nature that we learn as her children. It is not a mere set of technologies or production practices. It cannot be implemented the same way in all territories. Rather it is based on principles that, while they may be similar across the diversity of our territories, can and are practiced in many different ways, with each sector contributing their own colours of their local reality and culture, while always respecting Mother Earth and our common, shared values. The production practices of agroecology (such as intercropping, traditional fishing and mobile pastoralism, integrating crops, trees, livestock and fish, manuring, compost, local seeds and animal breeds, etc.) are based on ecological principles like building life in the soil, recycling nutrients, the dynamic management of biodiversity and energy conservation at all scales. Agroecology drastically reduces our use of externally-purchased inputs that must be bought from industry. There is no use of agro-toxines, artificial hormones, GMOs or other dangerous new technologies in agroecology.
TWN, SOCLA, 2015	Agroecology is a science that draws on social, biological and agricultural sciences and integrates these with traditional knowledge and farmer's knowledge.
Via Campesina, 2015	Wezel et al. (2009) have observed that the word agroecology is variously used to refer to a science, a movement and a practice. In a book written by, and largely for, La Via Campesina (LVC), Machín Sosa et al. (2010:16, translated from the Spanish) similarly note that "for the social movements that make up LVC, the concept of agroecology goes much further than just ecological-productive principles. In addition to these, LVC incorporates social, cultural and political principles and goals into its concept of agroecology."
Agroecology Europe, 2016	Agroecology is considered jointly as a science, a practice and a social movement. It encompasses the whole food system from the soil to the organization of human societies. It is value-laden and based on core principles. As a science, it gives priority to action research, holistic and participatory approaches, and transdisciplinarity that is inclusive of different knowledge systems. As a practice, it is based on sustainable use of local renewable resources, local farmers' knowledge and priorities, wise use of biodiversity to provide ecosystem services and resilience, and solutions that provide multiple benefits

This holistic, trans- and multidisciplinary concept including science, landscape (from plot to farm and landscape) but also different disciplines, food systems is also recognized by the main International institutions (Table 2). Wezel et al (2009) identifies agroecology as a set of practices, a social movement and a scientific discipline deepening in the holistic overview of this discipline.

Table 3 Definitions of Agroecology used by governments in different countries

Country	Definition
Costa Rica, 2000	Science that pursues harmony between the objectives of agricultural activity and the sustainability of soil, water and vegetation resources, in relation to ecology-development.
USA, 2007	Agroecology can be defined broadly or narrowly. Loosely defined, agroecology often incorporates ideas about a more environmentally and socially sensitive approach to agriculture, one that focuses not only on production, but also on the ecological sustainability of the productive system. This definition implies a number of features about society and production that go well beyond the limits of the agricultural field. At its most narrow, agroecology refers to the study of purely ecological phenomena within the crop field, such as predator/prey relations, or crop/weed competition.
Venezuela 2009	Agroecology is understood as the science whose principles are based on ancestral knowledge of respect, conservation and preservation of all natural components of sustainable agroecosystems at any scale or dimension.
España, 2012	As a practice, agroecology proposes the design and sustainable management of agroecosystems with ecological criteria (Altieri 1995, Gliessman, 2007) through forms of collective social action and participatory development proposals that promote forms of production and marketing of food and other agro-livestock products that contribute to respond to the current ecological and social crisis in rural and urban areas (Sevilla-Gumán and Woodgate, 2013). As a theoretical and methodological approach, agroecology constitutes a multidisciplinary and pluriepistemological strategy for the analysis and design of forms of participatory management of natural resources applying ecological concepts and principles, linked to postponed alternatives of local development (Norgaard, 1994, Guzmán et al. 2000).
Nicaragua, 2013	As a science agroecology provides the scientific basis for sustainable agriculture. It appropriates several disciplines for the analysis of all types of processes of agricultural activity, with the purpose of understanding the functioning of mineral cycles, energy transformations, biological processes and socioeconomic relationships.
France, 2014	Agroecology is the integrated use of nature's resources and mechanisms for the purpose of agricultural production. It combines the ecological, economic and social dimensions and aims to take better advantage of the interactions between plants, animals, humans and the environment.

The agroecology partnership linked to SCAR-Agroecology (2022) defined agroecology as a "dynamic and holistic approach to agriculture considered at the same time a science, a set of practices and a socio-political movement aimed at supporting the transition of agri-food systems towards more sustainable practices. It aims at connecting science, practice and society and to trigger the adoption of a set of policies aimed at sustainable agricultural practices."

The FAO identifies ten elements linked to agroecology and related to three pillars. The first linked to the land use such as (1) diversity, (2) efficiency, (3) recycling, (4) resilience and (5) synergies. The second associated with the food system such as (6) culture and food traditions or (7) circular and solidarity economy and the third related to (8) knowledge share such as co-creation and sharing of

knowledge and social aspects such as (9) human and social values and (10) responsible governance.

HLPE (2019) also identify 13 principles related with land and animal issues (1) recycling, (2) input reduction, (3) soil health, (4) animal health, (5) biodiversity, (6) synergy, the economic return (7) economic diversification and the more social and governance aspects (8) co-creation of knowledge, (9) social values and diets, (10) fairness, (11) connectivity, (12) land and natural resource governance and (13) participation.

All these definitions highlight the holistic approach of the use of a territory and the derived agri-food system. However, it is important that this definition is deployed in specific farm and agri-food practices linked to income, environment and social pillars adapted and prioritized to different environments and analysing how they fulfil the 10 elements of the FAO. This will facilitate the promotion, adoption and monitoring of agroecology practices across EU through the PAC support by the development of a set of policies promoting sustainable agricultural practices.

Agroecology researchers and stakeholder definition

A form to understand the meaning of agroecology from a policy point of view is to evaluate what are the end-users' perceptions, needs and interests and the future challenges (research search) of the agroecology sector. This can be approached through searches in internet (end-users) by analysing the grey literature and the web of science (researchers), respectively. In the present study a search in the grey literature from internet and the web of science of the topics "agroecology" and "organic farming" and both together was carried out defining three wording topics. Within each topic, a search of the most frequent words was carried out and analysed. The analysis consisted of (i) the distribution of the most frequent words in the three sustainability pillars (economic, environment and social) and (ii) the distribution of each sustainability pillar within each topic between the web of science and the grey literature. We approached this wording analysis considering the two-words search, because the terms associated with one-word were too general and the ones linked to three-words too specific.

Transition is the most relevant word for the agroecology topic (Figure 1), while agricultural production and sustainable development are the most important words in the case of the organic topic, probably because the system is already clearly defined. It can be seen that both sustainability and transition are also the most important mentioned words when agroecology and organic farming topics were evaluated together.

The analysis of the most frequent words within each of the three sustainability pillars for both agriculture and organic farming topics shows very rich results (Figure 2). **Production** (as economic activity) in the agroecology topic is associated with specific land management linked to cereals (wheatgrass), vegetables (greenhouse), permanent crops (viticulture), mixed farming (integrated crop-livestock) and also system management (agroforestry, integrated pest-management). These are different from those described in organic farming topic dealing with more specific systems (aquaculture, horticulture), food quality (polyaromatic hydrocarbons, polyunsaturated fatty-acids) and specific management (pre-harvesting interventions...) with some common words among both topics such as greenhouse production. Production procedures are well-known within the organic farming systems, so they are more focused on quality and harvest management not linked to the organic rules.

Figure 1 Most frequent two-words in the agroecology (top), organic farming (middle) and agroecology+organic (bottom) farming papers

From an **environment** point of view, *arbuscular mycorrhizal* as well below-ground interactions among different species were shared among both organic and agroecological topics, being more specific the words of the organic farming topic.

From a **social perspective**, the interaction among stakeholders is key for the **agroecology** topic, while consumption and commerce are more relevant for the organic farming topic (Figure 2).

Figure 2 Over 0.1% one-wording search distribution of agroecology (top) and organic farming (bottom) within the global (internet + web of science databases).

From the sustainability analysis, it can be concluded, that most of the words are related with cropping systems and crops but not with livestock systems. This fact highlights a more prominent community working in cereals whereas grasslands and grazing systems appear less relevant. With regard to the land management the most cited words are “cover crops” but also with less relevance “crop rotation” and “plant protection products” appeared. When the **agroecology topic** is evaluated in an exclusive way, the most mentioned keyword is food system and the benefits of agroecology (ecosystem services, species richness and climate change). The system approach also appears linked to the organic farming topic, having the cropping system more relevance than the livestock or grassland management. The most relevant practices are related to arable crops such as pest control, cover crops, crop livestock, crop production. With regard to the **organic farming topic**, that also includes the systemic approach the farming systems, organic farming but provides a high relevance to the soil (organic carbon, soil organic, soil fertility....). Cover crops and crop rotations are the most relevant land practices related to arable crops, but livestock also appears mainly linked to organic dairy. Grasslands are not evaluated again. This means that the main research of agroecology and organic farming systems are related to arable crops (cover crops, crop rotation, pest management), but not to crop diversification or livestock. Key aspects in the management, such as fertilization, are not mentioned which is especially relevant when we consider grassland management receiving more than the 50% of the nitrogen fertilization in the EU, also considering the largest share of grassland of the EU agricultural land, followed by cereals (Figure 3)

Figure 3 Share Nitrogen output in the EU countries as average 2005-2009s (Eurostat 2011)

The common words between production and environment for the agroecology topic are more related with plot management in general terms, while this is much more concrete in the case of the **organic farming topic**. This probably highlights the fact that management is more clearly known under organic conditions. The keywords shared between the environmental and social component are related to resilience and interactions in the case of the **agroecology topic** but with multifunctional landscapes in the case of the **organic farming topic**. The relationship between the production and social aspects in the **agroecology topic** is related with climate smart agriculture and nutritional properties, being the last shared by the **organic farming topic** which have others such as innovative biorefinery,

production conditions, artificial intelligence and nutritional properties. Finally, the common words shared among all of them are agroecological principles and agroecological transition.

With regard to the **production** comparative among the end-users (grey-literature) search and the research (web of science) in the **agroecology topic**, it can be seen that the unique common word between the researchers and grey-literature is the monitoring through the sustainability indicators (Figure 4). Nowadays, researchers are more based in global concepts related with the agroecological systems (regenerative, conventional, industrial innovations) but also approaches, management and sustainability. However, the search of the grey-literature is more based on innovative forms of solving specific challenges dealing with landscape, grassland, arable crops concerns (greenhouse production, soil-phosphorus availability, integrated pest management). The **organic farming topic** common words among the research and the grey literature are related to aquaculture production and nutritional properties. There are important challenges to be overcome in the case of the grey-literature search, that are generally and poorly addressed by the research. This is notably intensified when comparing both organic farming and agroecology topics together, with no common words, being again more general the evaluation of researchers and more specific the ones carried out by the end users.

The comparison among the search results of the end-users and the research within the **environmental** section (Figure 5) reveals that the **agroecology topic** search shows that end-users are indeed more worried about how to obtain benefits from the interaction with the different components, including legumes (biological nitrification, aboveground vegetation, belowground interactions...), while the researches are more focussed on general challenges (pollination, biodiversity, crop-livestock integration). A similar result was found when the **organic farming topic** is evaluated where only antibiotic resistance, sustainable agriculture and arbuscular mycorrhizal are common among the researchers and the grey literature. Common web of science and grey literature search within the joint **organic farming and agroecology topic** are linked to biodiversity indicators, agroecology principles and agroecology transition. In this case, some of the specific grey literature and web of science words are quite similar but not written in the same way (i.e. scientific literature vs agroecology-scientific literature, biodiversity conservation vs biodiversity management).

From a **social** perspective (Figure 6), the **agroecology topic** has a larger amount of relevant words than the organic or the agroecology and organic topic, being more important from a grey-literature than from a research point of view. Within the agroecology topic the researchers are more focussed on the analysis of the cross-border cooperation, information and on the evaluation and the interaction of multiple actors, as happens in **organic farming topic**. When analysing the social component of the agroecology and organic farming topic, the agroecology principles and agroecological transition are common findings in the research and end-user search, being the grey-literature more based on the delivery and management of the socioeconomic principles, while the research is more linked to the transition, territories and cultural aspects.

Figure 4 Most frequent production 2-keywords in the agroecology (top), organic farming (centre) and agroecology+organic farming wording groups (bottom) for the global (web of science + internet) and research (web of science) searches.

Figure 5 Most frequent environment 2-keywords in the agroecology (top), organic farming (centre) and agroecology+organic farming wording groups (bottom) for the global (web of science + internet) and research (web of science) searches.

Figure 6 Most frequent social 2-keywords in the agroecology (top), organic farming (centre) and agroecology+organic farming wording groups (bottom) for the global (web of science + internet) and research (web of science) searches.

We can conclude that transition and sustainability are the most relevant aspects for agroecology and organic farming. Researchers are more interested in general aspects dealing with global aspects (types of agriculture) while the end-users are more focussed on specific management, probably trying to solve their day-today challenges from a productive perspective. From an environment perspective, there are some big end-user challenges already considered by the researches such as antibiotic resistance or arbuscular mycorrhiza. From a social perspective, the organic farming topic has not relevant social research more focussed on agroecology, however, organic end-users searches for aspects related with e-commerce, life-style, consumption, transition or cooperation. The common search within the agroecology+organic farming wording groups shows that is based on agroecology as agroecology principles and transition is a matter for both end-users and researchers, being the first more interested in specific aspects (socio-ecological trade-offs, socio-economic principles or agriculture regulations) and the second ones on more general aspects (biocultural landscapes, socioecological transition and agroecology territories).

Agroecological searches are more general and organic farming searches mostly focussed in very specific sectors (horticulture, viticulture, aquaculture, strawberry), while agroecology is mostly linked to cereal, grasslands, and livestock/cereal/grasslands interactions. The environment analysis is mostly based on agroecology, but also on soils and efficiency use of the resources. The main aspects related to the social perspective are around bioeconomy, commerce, innovation, multi-actor, cooperation, governance, and multidisciplinary. In general, the queries linked to grey literature are more related to specific issues, while the researchers are more interested in demonstrating the global benefits of both agroecology and organic farming systems.

Agroecology international policies

A good summary of the historic perspective of the CAP, can be seen in the AGFORWARD EU FP7 project policy deliverable (Mosquera-Losada et al. 2017). The CAP has undergone through different deep changes since started, with an important initial goal of feeding Europeans and regulating markets. Nowadays, it has been converted into a tool to sustain landscape and agriculture management by ensuring social benefits and environmental care, as can be seen in the post-2020 CAP objectives (Figure 7). The CAP aims at achieving the following general objectives:

- (a) to foster a smart, resilient and diversified agricultural sector ensuring food security;
- (b) to bolster environmental care and climate action and to contribute to the environmental- and climate-related objectives of the Union;
- (c) to strengthen the socio-economic fabric of rural areas.

These three objectives are deployed in 10 objectives, three of which are related with the economic, three with environment, three with social and one with innovation and knowledge specific objectives. It includes three economic goals including the increase of competitiveness, ensure fair income and the rebalance of the power in the value chain. Moreover, it also includes three environment objectives such as the climate change action, environmental care and the preservation of the landscape and biodiversity. Lastly, it includes three social objectives dealing with the protection of the food and health quality, the construction of vibrant rural areas and the support to the generational renewal besides the 10th horizontal objective related to the knowledge and innovation.

Figure 7 Post-2020 CAP aims (black), FAO agroecology elements (green) and EU linked strategies (red)

The post-2020 CAP aims fulfils the EU strategies aligned with the different UN, pan-European and European commitments but also provides a clear response to the agroecology elements identified by the FAO as shown in Figure 7. The **economic CAP objectives** (competitiveness, fair income and food value chain) aligns very well with the bioeconomy, circular economy and farm to fork European strategies that can be associated with the agroecology FAO elements linked to efficiency, recycling and circular economy and solidarity economy. The **environment post-2020 objective** (climate change, environmental care and landscape) are well related with the climate change, biodiversity and forest strategies and aligned with the resilience and diversity FAO agroecology elements. Finally, the **post-2020 social CAP aims** (rural areas, food and health and generational renewal) are related to the EU strategy for rural revival and indeed aligned with the human and social values and the culture and food traditions agroecology elements. This means that EU CAP aims at fulfilling the sustainability goals through the economic support provided to farmers by the CAP to implement the EU strategies, fully aligned with the agroecology elements. Finally, the knowledge and innovation objective is directly related to the knowledge share and co-creation agroecology element. Therefore, EU sustainability should use agroecology principles to foster sustainability in Europe. In fact, the new SCAR-Agroecology partnership is funded under the premise that “Agroecology is an approach with the potential to address and provide the response to these challenges, building on natural, biological interactions while using state-of-the-art science and technology as well as basin innovation on farmers` knowledge and tested best practices.” This means that agroecology transition should be fostered by a resource efficiency use linked to the agroecosystem level and the transformation of the food systems as indicated the FAO HLPE report (HLPE 2019) and the FAO TAPE Tool (2019) as described the European partnership under Horizon Europe: accelerating farming systems transition: agroecology living labs and research infrastructures, as shown by Figure 8.

Figure 8 Agroecology transition levels (SCAR-AGROECOLOGY, 2022, based on HLPE 2019 and Gliessman 2007).

Agroecology European policies

The balanced economic, environmental and social objectives have to be fulfilled with the EU CAP funds which represents the 31% of the total EU budget through the implementation of the strategic plans at national level. Member states have to provide a set of output, result and input indicators to the before mentioned objectives to demonstrate they are reached as shown in the Annex I of the Communication 392(2018) final of the proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the council (EU 2018).

An important difference of the post-2020 CAP is the proposal by member states of strategic plans and the establishment of the Common Monitoring and Evaluation Framework that will cover all the instruments of the CAP: the CAP strategic Plans, and other elements such as parts of the Common market organisation or specific scheme. This performance is going to be measured in relation to the objectives of the policy by using a set of common indicators. The indicators will consider the (i) context indicators as pertinent as they reflect relevant aspects of the general trends in economy, environment and society and are likely to have an influence on performance, (ii) targeted indicators by prioritization of those that reflect as close as possible whether the supported intervention (the way that the specific CAP objectives are pursued) contributes to achieving the CAP objectives versus established baseline and using clear definitions, and (iii) impact indicators linked to a multi-annual assessment of the policy performance. But the annual policy performance follow-up will rely on the full list of (iv) output indicators which will link annually the expenditure with the performance of policy implementation, this will have an annual basis and relies on a list of (primarily already available) output indicators, and (v) the reliability of relevant performance indicators can be facilitated by synergies between statistical and administrative data, but requires the presence of a system of quality controls.

Within the post-2020 CAP, there are two important concepts, the *intervention* (support instrument with a set of eligibility conditions as specified by the Member States in the CAP Strategic Plans based on a type of intervention as provided for in this Regulation) and the *operation* (meaning either a project, contract, action or group of projects selected under the programs concerned or in the context of financial instruments, a programme contribution to a financial instrument and the subsequent financial support provided to final recipients by that financial instrument).

An annual performance review is foreseen as the key element of the ongoing monitoring and steering of policy implementation. In order to make an annual performance review operational, adequate output indicators and result indicators will have to be submitted jointly in an annual report on the implementation of the CAP Strategic Plan, the so-called Annual Performance Report. Member States will report annually on realised output and expenditure as well as distance to targets set for the whole period, expressed as values of result indicators.

This monitoring exercise will serve to overcome the fact that most of the previous CAP actions were not successful due to the fact of results control, being the post-2020 CAP more linked to the payments by results concept. The post-2020 also recognizes a relevant need which is the farm advisory services promotion needed to help farmers to extensify their ways of farming through the needed agroecology transition.

Agroecology and the CAP specific objectives, impact indicators, result indicators and output indicators

Economic objectives

Support viable farm income and resilience

The impact indicators intend to evaluate the economic position of agricultural income with regard to the general economy and its variability in general terms and compare the viability of the income with regard to other agricultural sectors. Moreover, the territorial balance of agriculture is analysed compared with areas with natural constraints (ANCs). Areas with natural constraints are identified by member states as mountain areas (Figure 9), areas with biophysical criteria (low temperature, dryness, excess soil moisture, limited soil drainage, unfavourable texture and stoniness, shallow rooting depths, poor chemical properties and steep slopes) not representing more than 10% of their total agricultural land, and those north of the 62nd parallel mostly affecting Finland and Sweden (EU 2022). From this impact indicator, data related with the areas with natural constraints can be assumed as linked to agroecology, as in those areas intensive farming systems are usually not adopted by farmers due to the limitation in the production response. ANCs budget receives the 16% of the total EAFRD. However, the impact analysis is based on a territorial basis, but not on an agricultural basis, considering for example organic farming systems or the inclusion of agroecology/agroforestry management practices.

Attending the result indicators, they are only linked to those interventions supported by the CAP, which limits the whole country understanding but provides insights about the CAP support within the member states agricultural systems. The result indicators are related to:

1) The share of utilised agricultural area (UAA) defined as the total area taken up by arable lands, permanent grassland, permanent crops and kitchen gardens used by the holding (including those uses as common lands and independently of the tenure type) covered by income support to standards and good practices and subject to conditionality. The standards and good practices associated with utilised area are explained in the Annex, being some of the areas related to the conditionality section climate and environment issues that can be understood as part of agroecology practices (crop rotation, no bare soils, maintenance of non-productive features...). This result indicator is associated with the whole area supported by the CAP in Europe as all of them have to fulfil conditionality needed to receive the basic income support based on the CAP entitlements.

Figure 9 European mountain areas (EEA 2010)

2) Risk management linked to the share of farmers with CAP risk management tools, that does not distinguish among types of farming systems or practices (agroecology, organic farming...) and therefore does not allow to analyse the better adaptation of these practices compared with intensive farming systems.

3) Percentage of additional support per hectare redistribution to smaller farms, usually linked at more sustainable land management, but not exclusively, that should be further deployed.

4) Percentage of enhanced support per hectare to farms in areas with specific needs, that should distinguish between the different types of farming systems and practices.

Recommendation: The impact indicators linked to support viable farm income and resilience should consider the economic position of agricultural income under different farming systems such as those including organic, agroecology and agroforestry practices. This will better support the understanding of the efficiency, recycling and circular and solidarity economy agroecology elements defined by FAO. Even though, the result indicators linked to support viable farm income and resilience are looking for favouring some less intensive systems (specific needs, small farms, general income support linked to conditionality options) all of them are paid to both intensive and extensive farming systems with different degrees of the sustainability approach, which are not considered as planned by the Annex I of the EU communication (2018) 392. Differentiate among farms that are using agroecology or agroforestry practices or organic farming is indeed needed to better understand the “support viable farm income and resilience across the European Union to enhance food security” from both supply and quality food guarantee. This better approach will help to understand the efficiency, recycling and circular and solidarity economy agroecology elements highlighted by the FAO.

Enhance market orientation and increase competitiveness, including greater focus on research, technology and digitalization

The impact indicators are just two, (i) increasing farm productivity by providing a productivity factor and the (ii) agri-food trade imports and exports to evaluate the evolution in reducing the imports for agriculture linked to sustainability. The first one can be caused by an intensification of the system as no link to the way of farming is analysed, while the second is more related with sustainability and can be linked to better use of internal resources in the farm, the so called ecointensification.

The result indicators are related to the (i) share of farmers linked to coupled support for improving competitiveness, sustainability or quality in sectors in difficulties, but usually coupled support are linked to intensive systems, and (ii) farm modernisation linked to investment support to restructure, modernise the farm including to improve resource efficiency, but not all this modernisation is associated with the sustainability as part may not include the improvement of the resource efficiency.

Recommendation: The impact indicators linked to *Enhance market orientation and increase competitiveness, including greater focus on research, technology and digitalization* are key to promote sustainable agri-food systems. However, there is not a proposal that accounts how these indicators differentiate between intensive agriculture and agroecology and organic farming systems, which limits the sustainability accounting and performance of the less intensive farming systems. This analysis will foster the benchmarking among farming systems and practices mainly linked to the circular and solidarity economy FAO agroecology elements. The results indicators related to *Enhance market orientation and increase competitiveness, including greater focus on research, technology and digitalization* should also differentiate among farming systems allowing to benchmark them as part of the sustainable goals of the CAP. This will help to better benchmark the outputs of the efficiency as an agroecology element proposed by the FAO.

22

Improve the farmers' position in the value chain

This impact indicator is related to the value chain objective, associated with the (i) improvement of farmers' position in the food chain, by determining the value added for primary producers in the food chain.

Two result indicators, namely (i) better supply organisation linked to producer groups, organisations, local markets, short supply chains and quality schemes and (ii) concentration of supply through the quantification of the share of value of marketed production by producer with operational programmes are indeed related to the agroecology perspective by linking resource use and product selling linked to short value chains and farmer organisations, which could indeed transform the way of farming through a better targeted product selling to urban surrounding areas.

Recommendation: The impact indicator linked to *Improve the farmers' position in the value chain* is clearly linked to those short value chains associated with agroecology practitioners, however, the lack of differentiation among farming systems definitely limits the accounting and monitoring and therefore benchmarking of the different farming systems and practices that are key to promote sustainable agri-food systems. The result indicator linked to *Improve the farmers' position in the value chain* is key to understand the human and social values, culture and traditions, the efficiency, recycling and circular and solidarity economy and synergy components described by the FAO. However, the data gathering should take into account the different farming systems and the improvement they cause when a comparison among agroecology, organic and intensive farming systems and practices are carried out.

The output indicators linked to the economic part of the CAP can be structured as shown in Table 4.

Table 4 Economic Intervention, CAP outputs indicators, FAO elements, CAP objectives and EU strategies dominant relationships

Broad type of intervention	Outputs indicators	FAO components	CAP objectives	Strategy
CAP support	O.3 Number of CAP support beneficiaries	circular and solidarity economy	Fair income, competitiveness	Green Deal
Decoupled direct support	O.4 Number of ha for decoupled DP	circular and solidarity economy	Fair income, competitiveness	Green Deal
	O.5 Number of beneficiaries for decoupled DP	circular and solidarity economy	Fair income, competitiveness	Green Deal
Coupled support	O.9 Number of ha benefitting from coupled support	circular and solidarity economy	Fair income, competitiveness	Green Deal
	O.10 Number of heads benefitting from coupled support	circular and solidarity economy	Fair income, competitiveness	Green Deal
Payments for natural constraints and other region specific constraints	O.11 Number of ha receiving ANC top up (3 categories)	circular and solidarity economy	Fair income, competitiveness	Green Deal
	O.12 Number of ha receiving support under Natura 2000 or the Water Framework Directive	circular and solidarity economy	Fair income, competitiveness	Green Deal
Investments	O.18 Number of supported on-farm productive investments	circular and solidarity economy	Fair income, competitiveness	Bioeconomy, circular economy
	O.19 Number of supported local infrastructures	circular and solidarity economy, recycling, efficiency	Fair income, competitiveness, food chain, responsible governance, synergies	Farm to fork
	O.21 Number of off-farm productive investments	circular and solidarity economy, recycling, efficiency	Fair income, competitiveness, food chain, responsible governance, synergies	Farm to fork

Most of the economic outputs indicators are related to the circular and solidarity economy as a FAO element, fair income and competitiveness and with the Green Deal aims. They are those associated with the global CAP payments associated with the coupled or decoupled support. However, the section of investments is linked to on-farm and off-farm infrastructures that may be linked besides the circular and solidarity economy to the recycling and efficiency FAO agroecology elements. The investment interventions support also on-farm and off-farm infrastructures that may be associated to different CAP goals such as fair income, competitiveness, food chain, responsible governance and synergies. However, as happened with the rest of the CAP economic objectives there is not distinction between the type of farming and practices that are used, which limits the potential of feedback for the CAP support to sustainability.

Recommendations: The economic output indicators, as well as the impact and result indicators should aim to benchmark different practice and farming systems to better understand the efficiency, the competitiveness and the food chain linkages to sustainability among them.

Environmental objectives

Contribute to climate change mitigation and adaptation, as well as sustainable energy

Four impact indicators are related with the first environment objective. The first impact indicator is linked to an index development associated with the improvement of the farm resilience, whose relationship with the agroecology depends on the way the index is developed. The second impact indicator is associated with the reduction of GHG emissions from agriculture that is good for sustainability but may be not linked to agroecology, for example the use of nitrous oxide production inhibitors that may cause an increase of nitrate leaching. The third impact indicator is related to the enhancement of the carbon sequestration which indeed aligns with the agroecology premises. The fourth deals with the circularity concept of the production of renewable energy from agriculture and forestry and therefore increases the sustainable energy in agriculture and it can be considered associated with the agroecology practices.

With regard to the result indicators linked to the first environment CAP objective are related to (i) climate change adaptation measured through the share of agricultural land under commitments to improve climate adaptation, and (ii) reducing emissions in the livestock sector linked to the support to reduce GHG emissions and/or ammonia. This may support a better manure management, which may be not associated with agroecology practices limiting the manure production such as grazing, but promoting indoor livestock farming systems with a high manure production. However, the last four

impact indicators namely (iii) Carbon storage in soils and biomass associated with the use of perennial herbaceous or woody crops linked to permanent grassland, agroforestry, forestry, peatlands... (iv) investments in renewable energy production capacity, including bio-based, if it is bio-based then it could be related to agroecology, (v) enhance energy efficiency measured through the energy savings in agriculture, and (vi) afforested land, through the development of afforestation, woodland creation and agroforestry are indeed linked to agroecology practices.

Recommendations: Impact and result indicators related to *Contribute to climate change mitigation and adaptation, as well as sustainable energy* are mostly linked with agroecology practices, however as happens with the economic impact indicators are not specifically related with the different practices and farming systems, which limits the understanding of the contributions of the different types of practices and farming systems to the CAP goal. Lacking of the global picture of benchmarking among practices and farming systems results reduces the possibility of fostering those more efficient in each biogeographic condition. Another important concern is related to the type of measurement, for example, the soil carbon storage increase in soils, which would allow to perceive carbon-credit income from carbon offsetting projects by farmers is not yet developed.

Foster sustainable development and efficient management of natural resources such as water, soil and air

The impact indicators associated with *Fostering sustainable development and efficient management of natural resources such as water, soil and air* are related to (i) soil erosion (reducing soil erosion as percentage of land in moderate and severe soil erosion on agricultural land) but not linked to soil health, (ii) air quality improvement (by reducing ammonia emissions from agriculture) but not other pollutants and three for water related with the (iii) reduction of nutrient leakage (focussed on nitrate leaching (% of ground water stations with N concentration over 50 mg-1 as highlight the nitrate directive)), (iv) water quality enhancement (gross nutrient balance on agricultural land) and (v) reducing pressure on water resource (by using the Water exploitation index plus (WEI+) understood as the mean of the annual total abstraction of fresh water divided by the long-term average freshwater resources). These activities are not associated with agroecology practices and are connected to both intensive and more extensive farming systems, but not differentiated. Most of the water impact indicators are related to nitrogen, but not other types of contaminants are considered such as organic compounds, heavy metals, etc.

The results indicators related to *Fostering sustainable development and efficient management of natural resources such as water, soil and air* only includes the interventions supported by the CAP and are based on (i) improving soils (share of agricultural land under management commitments beneficial for soil management), without an specification of those soil management beneficial practices, (ii) improving air quality associated to ammonia emissions and (iii) water quality, (iv) sustainable nutrient management both associated with the share of agricultural lands under management commitments for water quality and improved nutrient management, respectively. Moreover the indicator of share of irrigated land under commitments to improve the water balance is also part of the result indicator of (v) sustainable water use, but no differences between irrigations practices are established. Opposite to the impact indicators, the result indicators include two related with the environment/climate-related performance through investment and knowledge associated with the share of farmers with support (vi) in investment or (vii) for advice/training related to the care or environmental performance.

Recommendations: As happens for the previous impact and results indicators the linkage of these indicators to the intensive, organic or agroecological farming systems and practices is needed to better understand the performance of the CAP. Moreover, a more detailed number of variables to be measure to ensure soil health as well as air and water indicators are needed to reduce pollution and ensure nutrient efficiency.

Contribute to the protection of biodiversity, enhance ecosystem services and preserve habitats and landscapes

The impact indicators related to the *Contribution to the protection of biodiversity, enhance ecosystem services and preserve habitats and landscapes* are associated with the protection of biodiversity linked to both the increase of (i) farmland bird populations (Farm bird index) and (ii) enhanced biodiversity protection linked to the species and habitats (measured as Percentage of species and habitats of Community interest related to agriculture with stable or increasing trends), which relays on the “community interest related to agriculture species and habitats” described by each Member State. Therefore, they are modified considering to the biodiversity baseline and the Member State commitments with the biodiversity, which may differ among countries. Moreover, these indicators consider both the specific and habitat preservation but not the heterogeneity that favours this objective, probably linked to the landscape biodiversity. The third impact indicator is the (iii) enhanced provision of ecosystem services measured by the share of UAA covered with landscape features which generates landscape and plot heterogeneity needed to enhance biodiversity.

The results indicators associated with *Contribution to the protection of biodiversity, enhance ecosystem services and preserve habitats and landscapes* are five. Two of them are related to woody perennials: (i) supporting sustainable forest management (share of forest land under management commitments to support forest protection and management) and (ii) protecting forest ecosystems (share of forest land under management commitments for supporting landscape, biodiversity and ecosystem services. The (iii) preservation of habitats and species (share of agricultural land under management commitments supporting biodiversity conservation or restoration) and (iv) preserving landscape features (share of agriculture land under commitments for managing landscape features, including hedgerows) are two excellent indicators dealing with no protected areas, while the (v) result indicator Supporting Natura 2000 (Area in Natura 2000 sites under commitments for protection, maintenance and restoration) is better associated to those Member States protected areas, and therefore depends on the Member States possibilities to declare Natura 2000 sites and preserve them.

Recommendations: As happens for the previous impact and results indicators the linkage of these indicators to the intensive, organic or agroecological farming systems and practices is lacking. Biodiversity and enhancement of ecosystem services provision and habitats protection is otherwise well defined as it considers the plot and landscape level, but not the farm, which is the area of action of the CAP payments linked to the value chain.

The environmental output indicators can be seen in Table 5. Some of the outputs indicators are associated with (i) climate change resilience (risk management tools), the (ii) enhancement of environment/climate commitments in forest and agricultural areas beyond those mandatory requirements and linkages to the preservation of the genetic resources and (iii) the non-productive investments. As a (iv) horizontal output indicator the CAP describes a synthesis indicator related with the share of the area under environmental practices, which are nor specifically related to the land management.

Recommendations: The environmental output indicators are focussed on the resilience and the way how environment-climate activities can be fostered through the quantification of hectares, projects, investments and environmental practices implemented in the EU. However, they are not splitted by specific land management systems or practices, which limits the potential of the future use of these output indicators associated with intensive, agroecology and organic farming systems.

Table 5 Environmental Intervention, CAP outputs indicators, FAO elements, CAP objectives and EU strategies dominant relationships.

Broad type of intervention	Outputs indicators	FAO components	CAP objectives	Strategy
Risk management tools	O.8 Number of farmers covered by supported risk management instruments	environmental care	Resilience	climate change
Payments for management commitments (environment-climate, genetic resources, animal welfare)	O.13 Number of ha (agricultural) covered by environment/climate commitments going beyond mandatory requirements	Diversity	Environmental care	climate change /biodiversity
	O.14 Number of ha (forestry) covered by environment/climate commitments going beyond mandatory requirements	Diversity	Environmental care	climate change /biodiversity
	O.17 Number of projects supporting genetic resources	Diversity	Environmental care	climate change /biodiversity
Investments	O.20 Number of supported non-productive investments	Resilience	Environmental care	climate change
Horizontal indicators	O.31 Number of ha under environmental practices (synthesis indicator on physical area covered by conditionality, ELS, AECM, forestry measures, organic farming)	Resilience, diversity	Environmental care	climate change /biodiversity

Social objectives

Attract young farmers and facilitate business development in rural areas

The impact and result indicators associated with attracting young farmers and facilitate business development in rural areas are associated with (i) attracting young farmers (Evolution of number of new farmers) and (ii) the generational renewal (Number of young farmers setting up a farm with support from the CAP).

Recommendations: as happens with the previous impact and result indicators a distinction of these indicators among farming systems will be essential to understand the degree of improvement in different areas and farming systems.

Promote employment, growth, social inclusion and local development in rural areas, including bio-economy and sustainable forestry

The impact indicators associated with the *improvement of the response of EU agriculture to societal demands on food and health, including safe, nutritious and sustainable food, as well as animal welfare* are linked to the contribution to (i) jobs in rural areas (evolution of the employment rate in predominantly rural areas) and (ii) to growth in rural areas (Evolution of GDP per head in predominantly rural areas). However, the framework of these two indicators is not provided, while it is not clear what is meant by “predominantly rural areas”. The other two impact indicators are associated with a fairer CAP (Improve the distribution of CAP support) and the promotion of rural inclusion (Evolution of poverty index in rural areas). It would be advisable to link these impact indicators to different farming systems and the inclusion of traditional farming systems by the integration of the cultural values.

The result indicators are linked to (i) the growth and jobs in rural areas (evolution of poverty index in rural areas) that may be fostered through the (ii) rural bioeconomy development (number of bioeconomy businesses developed with support) and the (iii) digitalisation of the rural economy (rural population covered by a supported Smart Villages strategy), considering the (iv) connectivity of the rural areas (Share of rural population benefitting from improved access to services and infrastructure through CAP support) and the (v) promotion of the social inclusion (number of people from minority and/or vulnerable groups benefitting from supported social inclusion projects). The results indicators are associated with the promotion of the value chain diversification (result indicator linked to bioeconomy) and knowledge sharing associated with the connectivity, digitalisation and social inclusion, that will increase the job and population establishment in the rural areas.

Recommendations: Both the impact and the *improvement of the response of EU agriculture to societal demands on food and health, including safe, nutritious and sustainable food*, as well as animal welfare result indicators should consider the linkages to the different type of farming systems. The indicators should be better adapted to the different socio-economic conditions across the EU.

Improve the response of EU agriculture to societal demands on food and health, including safe, nutritious and sustainable food, as well as animal welfare

The impact indicators associated with the *improvement of the response of EU agriculture to societal demands on food and health, including safe, nutritious and sustainable food, as well as animal welfare* are linked to the (i) limitation of antibiotic use in agriculture (sales/use in food producing animals), (ii) the sustainable use of pesticides (Reduce risks and impacts of pesticides) and the (iii) response to consumer demand for quality food (Value of production under EU quality schemes (incl. organics)). All these impact indicators are really related to food security but should be monitored considering the different practices and farming systems.

In parallel, the result indicators linked to the *improvement of the response of EU agriculture to societal demands on food and health, including safe, nutritious and sustainable food, as well as animal welfare* are associated with the (i) antibiotic use limitation associated with livestock systems (Share of livestock units concerned by supported actions to limit the use of antibiotics (prevention/reduction), (ii) the sustainable use of pesticides (Share of agricultural land concerned by supported specific actions which lead to a sustainable use of pesticides in order to reduce risks and impacts of pesticides) and the (iii) the improvement of animal welfare (Share of livestock units covered by supported action to improve animal welfare).

Recommendations: All the proposed indicators are quite related with the agroecology, but in a limited form, antibiotics pesticide use are persistent in soils and some residues may be found that are not considered in this indicator. Moreover, animal welfare is clearly linked to organic and agroecology farming systems, that may not be associated with the improvement of animal welfare action, but with others such as the silvopastoralism as a form of agroforestry.

The output indicators linked to the social CAP objectives are mainly linked to rural areas youth promotion, establishment of farms, cooperatives and enterprises in the rural areas associated with networking promotion to foster synergies among actors to develop a set of projects, development strategies, operational fund/programme and quality schemes. Besides they are also associated with the promotion of animal welfare, health and biosecurity of food.

Recommendations: As mentioned before gathering these indicators associated with different types of value chain or farming systems is essential to better understand and therefore promote agroecology sustainable land use systems across Europe.

Table 6 Social Intervention, CAP outputs indicators, FAO elements, CAP objectives and EU strategies dominant relationships.

Broad type of intervention	Outputs indicators	FAO components	CAP objectives	Strategy
Decoupled direct support	0.6 Number of ha subject to enhanced income support for young farmers	Human and social values	Generational renewal	Rural revival
	0.7 Number of beneficiaries subject to enhanced income support for young farmers	Human and social values	Generational renewal	Rural revival
Payments for management commitments (environment-climate, genetic resources,	0.16 Number of livestock units covered by support for animal welfare, health or increased biosecurity measures	Human and social values	food and health	Rural revival
Installation grants	0.22 Number of farmers receiving installation grants	Human and social values	Generational renewal	Rural revival
	0.23 Number of rural entrepreneurs receiving installation grants	Human and social values	Generational renewal	Rural revival
Cooperation	0.24 Number of supported producer groups/organisations	Culture and food traditions	rural areas	Rural revival
	0.25 Number of farmers receiving support to participate in EU quality schemes	Culture and food traditions	rural areas	Rural revival
	0.26 Number of generational renewal projects (young/non-young farmers)	Human and social values	Generational renewal	Rural revival
	0.27 Number of local development strategies (LEADER)	Culture and food traditions	rural areas	Rural revival
Sectorial programmes	0.28 Number of other cooperation groups (excluding EIP reported under 0.1)	Human and social values	rural areas	Rural revival
	0.33 Number of producer organisations setting up an operational fund/program	Human and social values	Rural areas	Rural revival

Transversal objectives

Fostering knowledge innovation in agriculture and rural areas and encouraging their uptake

The unique impact indicator related to *fostering knowledge innovation in agriculture and rural areas and encouraging their uptake* is sharing knowledge and innovation (Share of CAP budget for knowledge sharing and innovation), which is deployed in three results indicators: (i) enhancing performance through knowledge and innovation (share of farmers receiving support for advice, training, knowledge exchange, or participation in operational groups to enhance economic, environmental, climate and resource efficiency performance), (ii) linking advice and knowledge systems (number of advisors integrated within AKIS (compared to total number of farmers)) and (iii) Digitising agriculture (Share of farmers benefitting from support to precision farming technology through CAP). The strong need of advice to implement more sustainable practices and farming systems to favour the needed transition makes necessary the distinction between intensive and more sustainable farming systems to ensure the needed transformation speed.

Finally, with regard to the output indicators they are associated with the European Innovation Partnership for agricultural knowledge and innovation (EIP) linked to the number of EIP operational groups and the number of advisors setting up or participating in EIP operational groups. However, there are several types of operational groups depending on the countries, for example the number of operational groups is high in Spain but the time span of the operational group is of two years. In Germany, there are few operational groups with a longer framework, needed to evaluate the impact on ecosystem services delivery. Again, there is no link between the type of operational group and the type of farming system or practice.

CAP conditionality, Pillar I, Pillar II and agroecology

The CAP is structured in conditionality, Pillar I fully paid by the EU which affects three types of agricultural areas: permanent grasslands, arable land and permanent crops, the so-called eligible and Pillar II co-funded by the EU and the Member states. Below we provide a description and a discussion of the potential of the conditionality, Pillar I and Pillar II as a way to fulfil the CAP objectives as the CAP strategic plans provided by the member states are not yet approved by the European Commission, and will be evaluated by the next AE4EU policy deliverable.

Conditionality

The conditionality includes a set of principles to allow farmers to receive direct payments and includes a set of statutory management requirements (SMR) under the Union law and the standards for good agricultural and environmental conditions (GAEC) of land established in the CAP strategic plans as shown in Annex I. They fulfil three specific areas: (i) climate and environment (ii) public health, animal health and plant health, and (iii) animal welfare.

Several of the SMR and GAEC can be considered as part of the agroecological principles related to the **climate and environment issues** (i) **climate change mitigation and adaptation** such as the permanent grassland maintenance (GAEC 1), ban of burning arable stubble (GAEC 3), (ii) **water** such as reduce phosphate (SMR 1) and nitrate (SMR 2) pollution sources, establishment of buffer strips along water courses (GAEC 4), use of farm sustainability tool for nutrients (GAEC 5), (iii) **soil** as reducing tillage (GAEC 6), no bare soils (GAEC 7), promoting crop rotation (GAEC 8), (iv) **biodiversity and landscape** linked to conservation of natural habitats (SMR 4) and performing activities linked to the maintenance of non-productive features and area to improve on-farm biodiversity (GAEC 9) such as agroforestry practices or ban on converting or ploughing permanent grassland in Natura 2000 sites (GAEC 10), (v) **public health**, animal and plant health associated with Food safety fulfilling their own (vi) food safety rules (SMR 5), (vii) ban of using in stockfarming substances with hormonal or thyrostatic action and beta-antagonists (SMR 6), (viii) identification and registration of animals associated with pigs (SMR 7), bovine (SMR 8) and ovine and caprine (SMR 9), (ix) animal diseases related to prevention, control and eradication of certain transmissible spongiform encephalopathies (SMR 10), (x) transmission animal diseases such as foot-and-mouth disease, swine vesicular disease and blue tongue (SMR 11), (xi) plant and protection products (SMR 12 and 13), and (xii) **animal welfare** associated with the minimum standards for the protection of calves (SMR 14), pigs (SMR15) and animal kept for farming purposes (SMR 16).

The conditionality includes some rules that directly affect the use of soil of agroecological practices such as crop rotation, nutrient sustainable use or agroforestry (including of woody perennials in the fields) among others. The conditionality considers the aspect of the value chain related to the food safety as well as climate change issues.

Pillar I

Pillar I is the instrument of the EU to pay the direct payments to farmers, as in the 2014-2020, the direct payments can be decoupled (linked to the land management) and coupled (linked to the crop and animal productivity). The types of interventions related to the decoupled direct payments are

1. the basic income support for sustainability to be paid under the conditions of this section of the Member States strategic plans. Each eligible hectare declared by a genuine farmer should get it. Depending on the member states, it could be based on historic entitlements or a uniform amount per hectare (ex. Eastern countries) once SMR and GAEC principles are fulfilled.
2. the complementary redistributive income support for sustainability related with the even payment per hectare at national level
3. the complementary income support for young farmers specifically for young farmers
4. the schemes for the climate and the environment, which defines the voluntary schemes for climate and environment (eco-schemes) provided by farmers that will support farmers that perform agricultural practices beneficial for the climate and the environment on eligible hectares. For this purpose, the member states should provide a list of agricultural practices considered beneficial for the climate and the environment that may be linked to agroecology. These practices should go beyond the (i) SMR and GAEC linked to the conditionality, (ii) minimum requirements for the use of fertilisers and plant protection products, animal welfare

and others mandatory member state requirements, (iii) the maintenance of agricultural area and should be different of those granted under the Environmental, climate and other management commitments of the Rural Development (Pillar II).

The types of interventions related to the coupled direct payments linked to specific sectors or production are usually paid per hectare or per animal on an annual basis, not related to agroecology principles:

1. the coupled income support mainly to support sectors and production or specific types of farming listed in Article 30 (cereals, oilseeds, protein crops, grain legumes, flax, hemp, rice, nuts, starch potato, milk and milk products, seeds, sheep meat and goat meat, beef and veal, olive oil, silkworms, dried fodders, hops, sugar beet, cane and chicory, fruit and vegetables, short rotation coppice and other non-food crops, excluding trees used for the production of products that have the potential to substitute fossil materials.
2. the crop-specific payment for cotton which are more limited than the first coupled direct payments as it will only pay that cotton of sound, fair and marketable quality, that established in lands defined by the member states which also defined the varieties to be paid.

Specific interventions and operations are defined for the different sectors.

Ecoschemes

As part of the voluntary support to farmers within the CAP Pillar I the commission provided a list of potential agricultural practices that eco-schemes could support and allocated to the European Green Deal targets such as (i) reduce by 50% the overall use and risk of chemical pesticides and reduce use by 50% of more hazardous pesticides by 2030, (ii) achieve at least 25% of the EU's agricultural land under organic farming, (iii) reduce sales of antimicrobials for farmed animals by 50% by 2030, (iv) reduce nutrient losses by at least 50% while ensuring no deterioration in soil fertility ; this will reduce use of fertilisers by at least 20% by 2030 and (v) bring back at least 10% of agricultural area under high diversity landscape features by 2030. Eco-schemes should cover the CAP specific objectives 4 (contribute to climate change mitigation and adaptation, as well as sustainable energy), 5 (foster sustainable development and efficient management of natural resources such as water, soil and air, 6 (contribute to the protection of biodiversity, enhance ecosystem services and preserve habitats and landscapes and 9 (improve animal welfare and address antimicrobial resistance, related to food and health).

The areas of environment, climate change and animal welfare actions under the CAP strategic plans are (a) climate change mitigation including the reduction of GHG emissions from agricultural practices, as well as maintenance of existing carbon stores and enhancement of carbon sequestration, (b) Climate change adaptation, including actions to improve resilience of food production systems, and animal and plant diversity for stronger resistance to diseases and climate change (c) Protection or improvement of water quality and reduction of pressure on water resources (d) Prevention of soil degradation, soil restoration, improvement of soil fertility and of nutrient management (e) Protection of biodiversity, conservation or restoration of habitats or species, including maintenance and creation of landscape features or non-productive areas (f) Actions for a sustainable and reduced use of pesticides, particularly pesticides that present a risk for human health or environment (g) actions to enhance animal welfare or address antimicrobial resistance.

The examples of agriculture practices are divided in (1) practices established in the EU policy instruments such as organic farming practices including conversion and maintenance of organic

farming and integrated pest management as highlighted in the sustainable use directive including buffer strips with management practices and without pesticide, mechanical, weed control, increased use of resilient pest-resistant crop varieties and species and land lying fallow its species composition for biodiversity purpose and (2) other practices including agroecology, husbandry and animal welfare plans, agroforestry, high nature value farming, carbon farming, precision farming improve nutrient management, protecting water resources, other practices beneficial for soil and other practices related to GHG emissions.

Agroecology CAP eco-schemes and research

As described in the following sections, the European Commission has provided a set of practices linked to the list of potential agricultural practices supported by the CAP eco-schemes that were searched in the web of science papers, whose results can be seen in Figures 10, 11 and 12 for the most triggering topics associated with plant, animal and farm management CAP eco-schemes practices as show in further sections (CAP 2014). The search included the web of science search, which were distributed attending to plant production, animal but also to farm level.

Plant

Figure 10 Results of the main plant production practices found in the agroecology and organic farming papers search.

Figure 10 shows the distribution of the papers related with the agroecology and organic farm topic practices at plant level, highlighting that crop rotation (20.9%) is by far the most relevant practice, followed by crop diversification (2.8%) and conservation agriculture (2.7%), with a minor set of studies related to plant variety (0.03%) and fertilization use (0.03%).

With regard to the animal management, the concept of animal robustness, fertility, longevity, genetic diversity and resilience are the most relevant practice (19.8%) followed by organic rules (0.08%) and feeding plans (0.02%) as highlighted in Figure 11.

Animal

32

Figure 11 Results of the main animal production practices found in the agroecology and organic farming papers search.

Figure 12 shows the results of the search at farm level, organic farming is by far the most relevant topic in research papers compared with the other activities linked at farm level.

Farm

Figure 12 Results of the main farm management practices found in the agroecology and organic farming papers search.

Trying to find a relationship between the eco-schemes practices with the different types of plant, animal and farm management, it was found that crop rotation, diversification and conservation are the most relevant for plant, animal state for animals and organic farming, nutrient management plan and manure management and storage are the most relevant for the farms.

Agroecology extent and eco-schemes promotion

Agroecology land use could be linked to two main global practices associated with the use of the biodiversity:

- 1.- Temporary biodiversity use associated with crop rotation
- 2.- Spatial biodiversity use at plot/landscape level

The analysis of the post-2020 Pillar I and the agroecology can be initially carried out considering the current agroecology practices extent (Mosquera-Losada et al. 2017) and how the “agroecology eco-schemes” practices of the post-2020 CAP were considered in the previous CAP 2014-2020 Pillar II.

Biodiversity temporary use

Crop rotation is mainly linked to annual crops change. Figure 13 shows the percentage of annual crops in Europe as per regional rural development programme in the last decade (years 2009, 2012, 2015 and 2018) that has been increased from the first to the last year shown. The lowest regional annual crops rate is placed in the South of Europe, probably due to the higher difficulties to grow cereals associated with water deficit of the crops, that makes more feasible to develop perennial crops.

Figure 13 Percentage of the RDP areas covered with annual crops.

Figure 14 shows the changes from cereal crops to other annual crops between 2009-2012, 2012-2015 and 2015-2018 and Figure 15 from wheat to other cereals in the same periods. With the exception of some areas in the North of Italy in 2009 where annual crops are transformed into perennial crops or in some regions of the South and North of Europe, UK and Estonia, most of the lands remains unchanged with cereals. Changes to grassland from cereals can be found in North of Spain, South of Italy and Sweden, which can be considered as part of the mixed farming systems. Mixed farms improve the soil of the croplands by introducing grassland and livestock rearing. On the other hand, most of central Europe changes the cereals by industrial crops, mostly annuals.

Annual crops evolution. Changes from cereals crops

Figure 14 Annual crops evolution changes from cereal crop lands.

Annual crops evolution. Changes from wheat to crops

Wheat is one of the most important cereals in Europe whose area mostly changes to industrial and also to root crops (Sweden) and to vegetables and other crops in the South of Spain. As happens with the cereals in most of Europe, wheat area is partially changed to industrial crops. Figure 1 of the Annex II shows that most of the wheat area do not change to other crops, with the exception of the maize, the most relevant forage crop in Europe. Changes from wheat to oat area are relevant in central Spain. As mentioned before, barley area (Figure 2 Annex II) changes mostly to cereals probably wheat with some exceptions that changes to fodder legumes or grassland. In central Europe barley area changes to root or industrial crops seems to be common. Barley area did not change to other cereals in most of Spain, but there are important changes in Northern Italy and Central Europe. In some areas such as UK, Sweden or Finland area changes from barley areas are produced to oat as this crop is better adapted to northern conditions. Most of the rye area changes to cereals (Figure 3 Annex II), but in some places it changes to industrial or permanent crops. In Spain, UK and Greece rye area rotates with grasslands, as part of the traditional sustainable farming systems in areas where intensification processes are not easy or profitable enough to be carried out. Rye area changes to different crops in Europe such as maize, rye, and barley. No changes are produced to rice or triticale (Figure 3 Annex II). Oat area changes initially to other cereals (Figure 4 Annex II) but in the most recent years it changes to permanent crops, industrial crops and mostly to Grasslands. Oats does not change too much in the last period (2015 and 2018) but it changes to wheat and sin some places to maize and mixed cereals for fodder (Italy). There is a huge potential to increase the temporary biodiversity in the croplands systems of Europe. The promotion of the crop rotation can be evaluated in the CAP 2014-2020.

Figure 16 Number of measures promoting rotation with legumes in the RDP of 2014-2020

Crop rotation is highly relevant to improve the soil, mostly when it is carried out with legumes. Figure 16 shows the number of operations promoting rotation with legumes in the 2014-2020 CAP. They are especially relevant in one region of the South of Italy and in several regions of France, also including

Navarra in Spain with more than 2 measures. Moreover, there are a large number of regions promoting this type of activity across Europe with one operation. The most relevant measures promoting these operations are the number 10 (agri-environment), the number 11 (organic farming) and the number 12 (Nature 2000). The main reasons behind this promotion argued by MS is the soil and fertility improvement as well as the sustainability, recognizing the important value of the legumes.

Figure 17 Number of measures promoting winter catch crops in the RDP of 2014-2020

Figure 17 shows the promotion of the winter catch crops in the RDP-2014-2020. Winter catch crops are promoted in several regions of France, UK and Finland usually linked to the measure 10 (agri-environment). The reasons behind are the same than for the rotation with legumes, the soil and fertility improvement but also the sustainability promotion.

Biodiversity spatial use

Polyculture share per regional rural development programme can be seen in Figure 18. They were estimated by implementing the Mosquera-Losada et al. (2017) methodology that uses the LUCAS database. The percentage of the area of the annual crop cover with at least two crops is rather small, with less than 12.5% of the share in most of the regions. Poland is the country with the highest share rate of this indicator.

Figure 18 Annual crops areas percentage covered with two or more crops per RDP area.

Figure 19 shows the promotion of the spatial biodiversity across Europe, with the operation of the polyculture or mixed culture, which are fostered in most of Europe with one measure.

Figure 19 Number of measures promoting mixed culture and polyculture in the 2014-2020 RDPs

Agroforestry is another relevant activity that diversifies the land (Figure 20), that has been promoted in many regions of Spain, Italy, Bulgaria and France as the measure 8.2. This measure is mostly linked to forestry, but also to others (Santiago-Freijanes et al. 2018a, 2018b, 2018c, Rodríguez-Rigueiro 2021; Mosquera-Losada et al. 2018, 2022) due to the difficulty of defining agroforestry.

Figure 20 Number of measures promoting agroforestry in the RDP of 2014-2020.

The organic farming can be also considered as part of the agroecology from a spatial and temporary use perspective from a land management point of view, that is mostly fostered across Europe with the measure 11 (Figure 21) with the reasons behind of sustainability, water quality, wildfire prevention and soil improvement.

Figure 21 RDP programmes activating organic farming measures in the RDP of 2014-2020.

Pillar II

Pillar II is a type of EU-Member state co-fund activity that fosters rural development by developing activities in a voluntary basis. They should go beyond conditionality and different from Pillar I activities payment. The different interventions compensate beneficiaries for costs incurred and income foregone result in from the commitments made and are paid annually. It includes 8 interventions:

1. environmental, climate and other management commitments: They may promote collective schemes and result-based payment schemes being farmers committed for a period of five or seven years.
2. natural or other area-specific constraints; The additional costs and income foregone shall be calculated in respect to natural or other area-specific constraints in comparison to areas which are not affected by natural or other area-specific constraints
3. Area-specific disadvantages resulting from certain mandatory requirements; linked to Natura 200, other nature protected areas and those included in river basin management lands
4. investments; Member States may only grant support under this type of interventions for tangible and/or intangible investments, which contribute to achieving the specific objectives set out in the CAP objectives. Support to the forestry sector shall be based on a forest management plan or equivalent instrument. Activities such as afforestation and non-productive investment related with the specific environmental and climate related objectives, investments in basic services in rural areas and investments in the restoration of agricultural or forestry potential following natural disasters or catastrophic events and investment in appropriate preventive actions in forests and in the rural environment.
5. installation of young farmers and rural business start-up;
6. risk management tools related to insurance schemes or contributions to mutual funds. Support is granted to cover the maximum rate of the 70% of the eligible costs.
7. Cooperation related to operational groups development
8. knowledge exchange and information related with the promotion of innovation, access to training and advice and exchange and dissemination of knowledge and information to reach the CAP objectives.

The Pillar II post 2020 will be developed in the next year and will be analysed in the next AE4EU deliverable.

Conclusions

The agroecology holistic concept has been defined by different disciplines and under different perspectives including plot, farm and landscape practices, the food system and the social perspective as a driver of sustainability and land use, which are adopted by different policy makers depending on their main challenges and innovations they have.

There is a higher interest in agroecology than in organic farming as demonstrates the higher weight of agroecology than organic farming in the joint topic search, being the agroecology topic more linked to general concepts mainly biodiversity and the organic farming more associated with specific management searches at sector, food system and land level. This fact is associated to the production and environmental pillars of sustainability.

In general, researchers are more interested in global aspects and systems while end-users are dealing with specific management issues, with a clear disconnection among what is investigated by researchers and what is searched by the end-users in the web site. Most of the end-users and

researchers agroecology and organic farming results are based on croplands being grasslands and livestock systems less considered in spite of the relevance of grasslands in Europe. The relationship between stakeholders is a subject for agroecology topic while consumption and commerce is key for the organic topic from a social perspective.

The EU strategy and the post-2020 CAP fit within the FAO agroecology elements and UN sustainability principles, however there is a clear lack of monitoring within the output, impact and result indicators of the economic, environmental and social post-2020 objectives which is a serious concern to really identify the use and benefits of agroecology practices in Europe.

The new CAP monitoring will be carried out by the member states but there is not a proposal of identifying (and allow also comparing) the impact, result and the outputs indicators associated with the intensive, organic and agroecology farming systems. This fact prevents from farming system performance benchmarking among extensive and intensive farming systems in the different Member States contexts.

The enhanced conditionality, the Pillar I and Pillar II policy measures are in line with the agroecology practices however they have not been promoted by the previous CAP, which should be considered when developed the strategic plans.

Conditionality SAR and GAEC are in line with the agroecological principles linked to climate change, water soil, biodiversity, public health and animal welfare. However, monitoring is essential.

Pillar I is not focussed on the type of farming without identification of the different types of farming systems (intensive, organic and agroecology) or practices

Crop rotation from a plant production perspective, animal robustness, fertility, longevity, genetic diversity and resilience from a livestock perspective and organic farming from a farm perspective are the most relevant keywords linked to the CAP eco-schemes from the literature review search. Most of the other eco-schemes practices for plant, animal and farm perspectives are not researched within the organic and the agroecology topics.

Agroecology in the CAP can be identified as the temporary and the spatial use of the biodiversity at multiple scales. There is only around 12.5% of polyculture/diversified rotations at spatial scale being. There is an increasing number of croplands areas in Europe with rather small crop changes over time.

Policy recommendations

Adopt the “Agroecology partnership” definition for agroecology a *“dynamic and holistic approach to agriculture considered at the same time a science, a set of practices and a socio-political movement aimed at supporting the transition of agri-food systems towards more sustainable practices. It aims at connecting science, practice and society and to trigger the adoption of a set of policies aimed at sustainable agricultural practices”* as a framework that should be further developed by providing the list of the set of farm and food system practices considering the agri-food system as a whole, considering the agroecology transition levels (incremental and transformational).

The development of the list of the set of farm and food system practices is essential to implement agroecology principles in the CAP fostering the agroecology transition. These practices can be integrated in the temporary and spatial biodiversity use of land and the food system.

Increase connections between the needs and the research with regard to the agroecology and organic farming topics through adequate research calls.

Increase funding for research associated with the eco-scheme practices and the association with the agroecology and organic farming topics, especially in grasslands.

Develop adequate monitoring systems that distinguishes the farming practices and systems (intensive, organic, agroecological) and indicators to benchmark them at local but also at member state level for the economic, environment and social sustainable indicators.

Develop adequate innovation environment and systems through the promotion of living labs where grasslands and croplands play an integrated role.

References

Altieri MA, 1995 Agroecology: principles and strategies for designing sustainable farming systems
Agroecology: principles and strategies for designing sustainable farming systems | FAO

Altieri MA, 1999. Bases científicas para una agricultura sustentable <http://agroeco.org/wp-content/uploads/2010/10/Libro-Agroecologia.pdf>

Altieri MA, Nicholls CI 2005 Agroecology and the Search for a truly sustainable agriculture
<http://www.agroeco.org/doc/agroecology-engl-PNUMA.pdf>

ASA, CSSA, SSSA, 2004 Agroecosystem Analysis
<https://dl.sciencesocieties.org/publications/books/articles/agronomymonogra/agroecosystems/frontmatter>

Brasil 2007, BRAZIL - National Policy for Technical Assistance and Rural Extension
<http://www.fao.org/faolex/results/details/en/?details=LEX-FAOC158754>

CAP 2014 Commission publishes list of potential eco-schemes.
https://ec.europa.eu/info/news/commission-publishes-list-potential-eco-schemes-2021-jan-14_en

Carrefour 2014. Agroecology. <http://www.carrefour.com/content/promoting-biodiversity-by-eating-honey-agro-ecology>

Costa Rica 2000. Reglamento de la ley de uso, manejo y conservación de suelos. :
<http://www.fao.org/faolex/results/details/en/?details=LEX-FAOC030828>

EEA 2010. Europe's ecological backbone : recognising the true value of our mountains. European Environment agency Copenhagen 2010 <https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/europes-ecological-backbone>

España 2012. Del desarrollo rural a la agroecología. Hacia un cambio de paradigma
<https://seminariodlae.files.wordpress.com/2012/10/c2-eduardo-sevilla-y-marta-soler.pdf>

EU 2018 <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/DOC/?uri=CELEX:52018PC0392&from=EN>

EU 2022 Areas of natural or other specific constraints (ANCs). https://ec.europa.eu/info/food-farming-fisheries/key-policies/common-agricultural-policy/income-support/additional-optional-schemes/anc_en

EUROSTAT 2011. Nitrogen balance in agriculture. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Archive:Nitrogen_balance_in_agriculture&oldid=65686

FAO 2021 Agroecology knowledge hub <https://www.fao.org/agroecology/home/en/>

France 2015 Fundamentation of agroecology <http://agriculture.gouv.fr/infographie-les-fondamentaux-de-lagro-ecologie>

Francis C, Lieblein G, Gliessman SR 2003. Agroecology the ecology of food systems. *Journal of sustainable agriculture* 22(3):99-118

Gliessman RS 2007 *Agroecology: the ecology of sustainable food systems*. CRC press 384 pages.

Guthman J. (2000) An agro-ecological assessment of grower practices in California, *Agr. Human Values* 17, 257–266.

HLPE Repot 2019 Agroecological and other innovative approaches. <https://www.fao.org/family-farming/detail/en/c/1238860/>

International Forum Agroecology 2015 Declaration of the International Forum for Agroecology. http://www.moreandbetter.org/file_download/240/Declaration-of-the-International-Forum-for-Agroecology-Nyeleni-2015.pdf

Mosquera-Losada, M.R., Santiago Freijanes, J.J., Pisanelli, A., Rois, M., Smith, J., den Herder, M., Moreno, G., Lamersdorf, N., Ferreiro Domínguez, N., Balaguer, F., Pantera, A., Papanastasis, V., Rigueiro-Rodríguez, A., Aldrey, J.A., Gonzalez-Hernández, P., Fernández-Lorenzo, J.L., Romero-Franco, R., Lampkin, N., Burgess, P.J. (2017). Deliverable 8.24: How can policy support the appropriate development and uptake of agroforestry in Europe? 7 September 2017. 21 pp. Deliverable 8_24 How can policy support agroforestry(1).pdf (agforward.eu)

Mosquera-Losada MR, Rodríguez-Rigueiro FJ, Santiago-Freijanes JJ, Rigueiro-Rodríguez A, Silva-Losada P, Pantera A, Fernández-Lorenzo JL, González-Hernández MP, Romero-Franco R, Aldrey-Vázquez JA, Ferreiro-Dominguez N 2022. European agroforestry policy promotion in arable Mediterranean areas. *Land use policy* (in press)

Mosquera-Losada, MR, Santiago-Freijanes, JJ, Rois-Díaz, M, Moreno-Marcos, G, den Herder, M, Aldrey-Vázquez, JA, Ferreiro-Domínguez, N, Pantera, A, Pisanelli, A y Rigueiro-Rodríguez, A (2018), Agroforestry in Europe: a land management policy tool to combat climate change. *Land Use Policy*, 78: 603-613. available at https://www.evise.com/co-author/?dgcid=invite_email_coauthoroutreach02648377#/LUP/submission/LUP_2018_357 [24 julio 2018]. OECD 2003 Agroecology. Agro-ecology is the study of the relation of agricultural crops and environment. <http://stats.oecd.org/glossary/detail.asp?ID=81>

Nicaragua 2013 Norma técnica obligatoria nicaragüense sobre caracterización, regulación y certificación de unidades de producción agroecológica <http://www.fao.org/faolex/results/details/en/?details=LEX-FAOC138639>

Norgaard R.B. (1984) Traditional agricultural knowledge: past performance, future prospects, and institutional implications, *Am. J. Agr. Econ.* 66, 875–878.

Rodríguez-Rigueiro FJ, Santiago-Freijanes JJ, Mosquera-Losada MR, Castro M, Silva-Losada P, Pisanelli A, Pantera A, Rigueiro-Rodríguez A, Ferreiro-Domínguez N 2021. Silvopasture policy promotion in European Mediterranean areas. *Plos One* 16(1)

Santiago-Freijanes, José Javier, Mosquera-Losada, María Rosa, Rois-Díaz, Mercedes, Ferreiro-Domínguez, Nuria, Pantera, Anastasia, Aldrey-Vázquez, José Antonio y Rigueiro-Rodríguez, Antonio (2018a), Global and European policies to foster agricultural sustainability: agroforestry. *Agroforestry Systems*: 1-16. available at <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s10457-018-0215-9> [3 marzo 2018].

Santiago-Freijanes, José Javier, Pisanelli, Andrea, Rois-Díaz, Mercedes, Aldrey-Vázquez, José Antonio, Rigueiro-Rodríguez, Antonio, Pantera, Anastasia, Vityi, A., Lojka, B., Ferreiro-Domínguez, Nuria y Mosquera-Losada, María Rosa (2018b), Agroforestry development in Europe: Policy issues. *Land Use Policy*, 76(March): 144-156. available at <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0264837717310670> [8 mayo 2018].

Santiago-Freijanes, José Javier, Rigueiro-Rodríguez, Antonio, Aldrey-Vázquez, José Antonio, Moreno-Marcos, Gerardo, den Herder, Michael, Burgess, Paul J. y Mosquera-Losada, María Rosa (2018c), Understanding agroforestry practices in Europe through landscape features policy promotion. *Agroforestry Systems*, 92(4): 1105–1115. available at <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s10457-018-0212-z> [19 febrero 2018].

Sevilla-Guzmán Woodgate G, 2013 Agroecología fundamentos del pensamiento social agrario y teoría sociológica *Agroecología* 8(2): 27-34

Third work network, SOCLA 2015 Agroecology key concepts, principles and practices. *Agroecology-training-manual-TWN-SOCLA.pdf*

USA 2007 United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) – Agroecology. <https://www.nal.usda.gov/afsic/sustainable-agriculture-definitions-and-terms-related-terms#term1>

Venezuela 2009 Ley de Salud Agrícola Integral- <http://www.fao.org/faolex/results/details/en/?details=LEX-FAOC083245>

Via Campesina 2013. La Via Campesina and agroecology. <https://viacampesina.org/downloads/pdf/openbooks/EN-12.pdf>

Wezel A, Bellon S, Doré T, Francis C, Vallod D, David C 2009. Agroecology as a science, a movement and a practice. *A review. Agronomy for sustainable development* 29:503-515

ANNEX I

Annex I. Conditionality

Areas	Main Issue	Requirements and standards	Main objective of the standard		
Climate and environment	Climate change (mitigation of and adaptation to)	GAEC 1	Maintenance of permanent grassland based on a ratio of permanent grassland in relation to agricultural area	<i>General safeguard against conversion to other agricultural uses to preserve carbon stock</i> <i>Protection of carbon-rich soils</i> <i>Maintenance of soil organic matter</i>	
		GAEC 2	Appropriate protection of wetland and peatland		
		GAEC 3	Ban on burning arable stubble, except for plant health reasons		
	Water	Water	SMR 1	Directive 2000/60/EC of 23 October 2000 of the European Parliament and of the Council establishing a framework for Community action in the field of water policy: Article 11(3)(e) and Article 11(3)(h) as regards mandatory requirements to control diffuse sources of pollution by phosphates	
			SMR 2	Council Directive 91/676/EEC of 12 December 1991 concerning the protection of waters against pollution caused by nitrates from agricultural sources (OJ L 375, 31.12.1991, p. 1): Articles 4 and 5	
			GAEC 4	Establishment of buffer strips along water courses ²	<i>Protection of river courses against pollution and run-off</i>
			GAEC 5	Use of Farm Sustainability Tool for Nutrients ³	<i>Sustainable management of nutrients</i>

² The GAEC buffer strips must respect, both within and outside vulnerable zones designated pursuant to Article 3(2) of Directive 91/676/EEC, at least the requirements relating to the conditions for land application of fertiliser near water courses, referred to in point A.4 of Annex II to Directive 91/676/EEC to be applied in accordance with the action programmes of Member States established under Article 5(4) of Directive 91/676/EEC

³ The Tool shall provide at least for the following elements and functionalities:

a) Elements

- Relevant farm information based on LPIS and IACS;
- Information from the soil sampling, on an appropriate spatial and temporal scale;
- Information on relevant management practices, crop history, and yield goals;

Areas	Main Issue	Requirements and standards	Main objective of the standard	
	Soil (protection and quality)	GAEC 6	Tillage management reducing the risk of soil degradation, including slope consideration	<i>Minimum land management reflecting site specific conditions to limit erosion</i>
		GAEC 7	No bare soil in most sensitive period(s)	<i>Protection of soils in winter</i>
		GAEC 8	Crop rotation	<i>Preserve the soil potential</i>
	Biodiversity and landscape (protection and quality)	SMR 3	Directive 2009/147/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 November 2009 on the conservation of wild birds (OJ L 20, 26.1.2010, p. 7): Article 3(1), Article 3(2)(b), Article 4(1), (2) and (4)	
		SMR 4	Council Directive 92/43/EEC of 21 May 1992 on the conservation of natural habitats and of wild flora and fauna (OJ L 206, 22.7.1992, p. 7): Article 6(1) and (2)	
		GAEC 9	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Minimum share of agricultural area devoted to non-productive features or areas • Retention of landscape features • Ban on cutting hedges and trees during the bird breeding and rearing season • As an option, measures for avoiding invasive plant species 	<i>Maintenance of non-productive features and area to improve on-farm biodiversity</i>

- Indications regarding legal limits and requirements relevant to farm nutrients management;
- A complete nutrient budget.

b) Functionalities

- Automatic integration of data from various sources (LPIS and IACS, farmer-generated data, soil analyses etc.) as far as possible, to avoid data input duplication for farmers;
- Two-way communication between PA/MAs and farmers allowed;
- Modularity and possibility to support further sustainability objectives (e.g. emissions management, water management)
- Respect of EU data inter-operability, openness and re-use principles;
- Guarantees for data security and privacy in line with best current standards.

Areas	Main Issue	Requirements and standards		Main objective of the standard
		GAEC 10	Ban on converting or ploughing permanent grassland in Natura 2000 sites	<i>Protection of habitats and species</i>
Public health, animal health and plant health	Food safety	SMR 5	Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 January 2002 laying down the general principles and requirements of food law, establishing the European Food Safety Authority and laying down procedures in matters of food safety (OJ L 31, 1.2.2002, p. 1): Articles 14 and 15, Article 17(1) ⁴ and Articles 18, 19 and 20	
		SMR 6	Council Directive 96/22/EC of 29 April 1996 concerning the prohibition on the use in stockfarming of certain substances having a hormonal or thyrostatic action and beta-agonists, and repealing Directives 81/602/EEC, 88/146/EEC and 88/299/EEC (OJ L 125, 23.5.1996, p. 3): Article 3(a), (b), (d) and (e) and Articles 4, 5 and 7	
	Identification and registration of animals	SMR 7	Council Directive 2008/71/EC of 15 July 2008 on identification and registration of pigs (OJ L 213, 8.8.2005, p. 31): Articles 3, 4 and 5	

⁴ As implemented in particular by:

- Article 14 of Regulation (EC) No 470/2009 and the Annex of Regulation (EC) No 37/2010,
- Regulation (EC) No 852/2004: Article 4(1) and Annex I part A (II 4 (g, h, j), 5 (f, h), 6; III 8 (a, b, d, e), 9 (a, c)),
- Regulation (EC) No 853/2004: Article 3(1) and Annex III Section IX Chapter 1 (I-1 b, c, d, e; I-2 a (i, ii, iii), b (i, ii), c; I-3; I-4; I-5; II-A 1, 2, 3, 4; II-B 1(a, d), 2, 4 (a, b)), Annex III Section X Chapter 1(1),
- Regulation (EC) No 183/2005: Article 5(1) and Annex I, part A (I-4 e, g; II-2 a, b, e), Article 5(5) and Annex III (under the heading ‘FEEDING’, point 1 entitled ‘Storage’, first and last sentences, and point 2 entitled ‘Distribution’, third sentence), Article 5(6), and
- Regulation (EC) No 396/2005: Article 18.

Areas	Main Issue	Requirements and standards		Main objective of the standard
		SMR 8	Regulation (EC) No 1760/2000 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 July 2000 establishing a system for the identification and registration of bovine animals and regarding the labelling of beef and beef products and repealing Council Regulation (EC) No 820/97(OJ L 204, 11.8.2000, p. 1): Articles 4 and 7	
		SMR 9	Council Regulation (EC) No 21/2004 of 17 December 2003 establishing a system for the identification and registration of ovine and caprine animals and amending Regulation (EC) No 1782/2003 and Directives 92/102/EEC and 64/432/EEC (OJ L 5, 9.1.2004, p. 8): Articles 3, 4 and 5	
	Animal diseases	SMR 10	Regulation (EC) No 999/2001 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 May 2001 laying down rules for the prevention, control and eradication of certain transmissible spongiform encephalopathies (OJ L 147, 31.5.2001, p. 1): Articles 7, 11, 12, 13 and 15	
		SMR 11	Regulation (EU) 2016/429 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 9 March 2016 on transmissible animal diseases (OJ L 84, 31.3.2016, p.1) Article 18(1), limited to foot-and-mouth disease, swine vesicular disease and blue tongue.	
	Plant protection products	SMR 12	Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 October 2009 concerning the placing of plant protection products on the market and repealing Council Directives 79/117/EEC and 91/414/EEC (OJ L 309, 24.11.2009, p. 1): Article 55, first and second sentence	

Areas	Main Issue	Requirements and standards		Main objective of the standard
		SMR 13	<p>Directive 2009/128/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 October 2009 establishing a framework for Community action to achieve the sustainable use of pesticides (OJ L 309, 24.11.2009, p. 71):</p> <p>Article 5(2) and Article 8(1) to (5)</p> <p>Article 12 with regard to restrictions on the use of pesticides in protected areas defined on the basis of the Water Framework Directive and Natura 2000 legislation.</p> <p>Article 13(1) and (3) on handling and storage of pesticides and disposal of remnants.</p>	
Animal welfare	Animal welfare	SMR 14	<p>Council Directive 2008/119/EC of 18 December 2008 laying down minimum standards for the protection of calves (OJ L 10, 15.1.2009, p. 7):</p> <p>Articles 3 and 4</p>	
		SMR 15	<p>Council Directive 2008/120/EC of 18 December 2008 laying down minimum standards for the protection of pigs (OJ L 47, 18.2.2009, p. 5):</p> <p>Article 3 and Article 4</p>	
		SMR 16	<p>Council Directive 98/58/EC of 20 July 1998 concerning the protection of animals kept for farming purposes(OJ L 221, 8.8.1998, p. 23):</p> <p>Article 4</p>	

ANNEX II

Annual crops evolution. Changes from wheat crops to other cereal

Figure 1 Annual crops evolution changes from wheat crop lands.

Annual crops evolution. Changes from barley crops

Figure 2 Annual crops evolution changes from barley crop lands

Annual crops evolution. Changes from rye crops to other cereals

Analysis of policy implementation at EU level and different EU countries and CAP strategies

Figure 3 Annual crops evolution changes from rye crop lands.

Annual crops evolution. Changes from oat crops to other cereals